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Development of a radon-in-water primary standard

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Abstract

The absence of a certified standard for radon-in-water presents a significant gap in environmental monitoring and water production quality control in compliance with EURATOM directive 2013/51. To address this, we developed a system to produce a radon-in-water primary standard derived from the radon primary standard available at LNHB, which is based on counting in defined solid angle (DSA). The radon certified by DSA counting was dissolved into a known quantity of water using a newly developed system that allows a loss-free transfer with ensured accuracy and reproducibility. To validate the production of this standard, multiple primary measurement methods were employed. Radon activity in water was determined using liquid scintillation counting, specifically the Triple-to-Double Coincidence Ratio (TDCR) method, which provides a direct and highly accurate measurement. Additionally, gamma-ray spectrometry was applied as an independent verification technique. Comparative analysis of these methods was conducted to assess their consistency and reliability in certifying the radon-in-water standard. The results demonstrated the effectiveness of our production method and confirmed the validity of the radon-in-water standard. However, our study also revealed subtle yet significant factors influencing gamma-ray spectrometry measurements, highlighting the need for careful consideration of such effects in future measurements. This work contributes to the establishment of a robust and reliable radon-in-water standard, filling an essential gap in the field and supporting improved traceability chain, environmental monitoring, radioprotection, and calibration of measurement systems.

Keywords: ²²²Rn-in-water, primary standard, TDCR counting, Gamma-spectrometry, LSC counting

1. Introduction

Radon (²²²Rn) is a naturally occurring radioactive gas that is widely studied due to its impact on public health. With a half-life of 3.8232 (8) days, radon decays by alpha transition into a series of radioactive progenies emitting themselves alpha and beta particles associated with gamma transitions. The entire decay chain can contribute to radiation exposure through inhalation or ingestion. The monitoring and regulation of radon concentrations, particularly in water, are crucial to mitigate potential health risks. In this context, the European Union has established specific limits and norms under EURATOM directives 2013/51 [1] to control radon exposure in drinking water. The parametric value for radon in water for human consumption is defined in the directives as 100 Bq·L⁻¹.

The ISO standards for radon measurement in water, including ISO 13164-4 for liquid scintillation counting (LSC) and ISO 13164-3 for gamma-ray spectrometry (GS), provide guidance on analytical methods. However, the lack of certified standards for radon-in-water remains a significant challenge for calibration and traceability efforts.

One of the main difficulties in radon-in-water calibration is the interference caused by ^{226}Ra and its progeny, particularly ^{210}Pb , in LSC measurements, as highlighted by [2]. This issue complicates accurate quantification and underscores the necessity of a reliable radon-in-water reference material. Previous interlaboratory comparisons, such as those organized by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) at Geel, Belgium [3] and the Institut de Radioprotection et de Sûreté Nucléaire (IRSN), France [4] have demonstrated a wide spread in the intercomparison results but these were performed without standardized reference value further emphasizing the gap in metrological traceability for radon-in-water analysis.

In order to fill the gap we have developed a system to produce a radon-in-water standard derived from the defined solid angle (DSA) radon primary standard developed at LNHB [5]. An amount of ^{222}Rn , certified by the DSA method, is dissolved in a known volume of water using a loss-free procedure, ensuring high accuracy and reproducibility. A second primary method is used in the standardization of the radon-in-water activity concentration, which is the Triple to Double Coincidence Ratio (TDCR) counting method. The two primary methods are systematically compared to assess their reliability in certifying the radon-in-water standard.

Gamma-ray spectrometry is also studied as a radon-in-water measurement technique where subtle effects were found to influence GS measurements. To better understand these effects, we conducted Monte Carlo simulations in addition to experimental measurements, which provided insights into their nature and impact. This work represents a significant step toward establishing a robust radon-in-water standard, addressing a critical need in environmental monitoring and radiological protection.

2. Methods and Materials

2.1 Measurement of ^{222}Rn in equilibrium with its short lived progeny.

The decay chain of ^{222}Rn can be simplified, as the contribution of ^{218}At , ^{218}Rn and ^{210}Tl can be neglected. At equilibrium the relative activity of these radionuclides vs. the activity of ^{222}Rn are respectively $2.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$, $2.2 \cdot 10^{-7}$ and $2.1 \cdot 10^{-4}$. Thus, the simplified decay scheme considered in this study is presented in Figure 1.

The relative activities of the radioactive daughters vs. ^{222}Rn activity at equilibrium can be calculated with the Bateman equations using the DDEP recommended half-lives and associated standard uncertainties [6]. The results are presented in Table 1.

The time needed for a closed sample to reach secular equilibrium between ^{222}Rn and its short-lived progeny is 5 hours. This time is governed by the half-life of ^{214}Pb , 26.9 (1) minutes. Therefore, all the measurements in this work started no earlier than 5 hours after the preparation of the corresponding samples.

The ingrowth of ^{210}Po is quite slow and the activity of this radionuclide and its radioactive daughters can be neglected in the ^{222}Rn measurement, as, due to the source preparation from gaseous ^{222}Rn , there is no initial ^{210}Po activity. After a delay of 3.8 days from source preparation, the relative activity of ^{210}Pb over the activity of ^{222}Rn is lower than $5 \cdot 10^{-4}$. Thus in our measurement conditions, the activity of ^{210}Pb can be neglected.

2.2 The radon-in-water system

General overview

The radon-in-water system has been specifically designed to establish a radon-in-water standard and to produce water samples with certified radon concentration (which will be referred to in the following as “radonated water”). This system lays down the basis for a traceability chain for the various radon-in-water measurements used in practice. The main objective is to link a primary standard of radon gas directly to a radon-in-water standard, which is achieved by loss-free dissolution of primary standardized radon in water. The key functional objectives of the design were as follows:

- i. Enable the transfer of ^{222}Rn certified by the DSA method to the system for production of radonated water;
- ii. Ensure a secure, airtight system operable from vacuum conditions to overpressure (minimum +1000 hPa);
- iii. Guarantee excellent, 100% loss free dissolution of radon in water,
- iv. Design a system which can be thoroughly cleaned after use and restored to a high-quality vacuum state,
- v. Facilitate sampling of the water or supply it by other means as required to disseminate the unit.

The preliminary concept has been developed through extensive testing over the past three years to achieve the optimal system design. This includes previous versions of the system, which are described in [7]. After this period of testing, we successfully constructed a complete system, shown schematically in Figure 2 and photographically in Figure 3. The entire setup is made of stainless-steel tubing and connectors, with the exception of the pump membrane, made of PTFE, and two glass tubes for visual monitoring of the water to check for absence of gas bubbles. This design choice avoids gas absorption on the system's walls.

The entire system is connected to a reference volume (V_{ref}), a high-precision pressure gauge (CPG2500 from Mensor), a temperature sensor (PT100), and a vacuum pump via volumes V_1 and V_2 . This part of the system is not used for producing radonated water but is essential for precise volume measurement, employing the technique outlined in [7]. Volumes V_3 to V_{19} are designated for radonated water production and are divided into two main sections: one for the LSC sampling process and the other for GS.

The circuit can be fully filled with water, the circulation pump enables bi-directional flow and supports vacuum conditions down to 10^{-6} hPa, as well as overpressures up to 1000 hPa. Water temperature is monitored by a PT100 sensor (T_1), and pressure by P_1 (PTI-S from Swagelok). The circuit is also connected to two additional volumes: V_{20} , through which the system is provided with dry and clean air (relative humidity below 3%), and V_{21} , which supplies the circuit with degassed water, ensuring that no gas is absorbed during the procedure described in Section 3.1.

The gamma-ray spectrometry branch

The GS sampling branch of the system comprises a set of five stainless steel volumes: four of 100 cm³ and one of 50 cm³ (GAZ 11). The GS branch is indicated in Figure 2 and the positions of the GAZ volumes can be seen in Fig. 3. These volumes are interchangeable at any time via VCR[®] connectors, which ensure an exceptionally tight and reproducible connection, enabling flexible geometries, provided that stainless steel containers are used. A close-up of the GAZ volumes is shown in Fig. 4. A key feature of this setup is that any GAZ volume can be directly connected to the primary radon standard system for cryogenic radon transfer. Each volume is precisely measurable and can be disconnected as required to calibrate various gamma-ray spectrometers.

The Liquid Scintillation Counting branch

The Liquid Scintillation Counting (LSC) sampling branch of the system is specifically designed to provide over 100 mL of radonated water for the preparation of liquid scintillation vials. The setup includes approximately 9 meters of narrow tubing (4 mm internal diameter), which enables precise sampling. This circuit can be isolated from the rest of the system and is connected to a Dispensette[®], which pushes pre-selectable amount of clean water through the tubing. Pushing with the Dispensette[®] allows high reproducibility and accuracy of the amount of the pushed water per push, which enables precise water sampling with the system. The narrow diameter of the tubing minimizes exchanges between the radonated water and the clean water used for sampling into the LSC vial (examples of the LSC sampling are shown in [7]). During the LSC sampling process, the needle is carefully inserted into the liquid scintillation vial and water is dispensed in the selected volume well below the surface of the liquid scintillator, in order to ensure no water reaches the air above the liquid level. Once sampling is complete, the mass of the sampled water is measured, and the vial is then topped up with scintillator to ensure no air bubbles remain when the vial is sealed. Note that as the water is denser than the organic liquid scintillation cocktails used, it stays below the cocktail and no radon escapes during the mass measurement step.

Standardization of the radon-in-water concentration

By design, the radon-in-water concentration is directly linked to the DSA primary standard of radon gas but can also be standardised by the Triple-to-double coincidence ratio (TDCR) counting method. In the standardisation by the defined solid angle measurement, the activity per unit of volume of ²²²Rn in the water (A_V) is given by:

$$A_V = \frac{A_\Omega}{V_{sys}} k_V \quad (1)$$

where A_Ω is the radon activity transferred to the system, which is certified by the DSA measurement, V_{sys} is the volume of the system filled with water and k_V is a corrective factor accounting for the condition of the water during the filling of the system and the transfer of the radon to the water (e.g. temperature gradient in the water filling the system, potential existence of miniature bubbles, etc.). The relative standard uncertainty of A_V is given by:

$$\delta_{A_V} = \sqrt{\delta_{A_\Omega}^2 + \delta_{V_{sys}}^2 + \delta_{k_V}^2} \quad (2)$$

where δ_{A_Ω} , $\delta_{V_{sys}}$ and δ_{k_V} are the relative standard uncertainties of A_Ω , V_{sys} and k_V , respectively. With this configuration, it is possible to calculate the volume activity in $\text{Bq}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$, fully complying with EURATOM directive [1]. Additionally, by considering the water density under the experimental conditions, the mass activity can be determined in $\text{Bq}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. This method, therefore, provides two distinct measurement parameters for the same experiment.

In the standardization by TDCR counting, the mass- activity of ^{222}Rn in the water is given by:

$$A_m = \frac{A_{TDCR}}{m} \quad (3)$$

where A_{TDCR} is the activity of ^{222}Rn in the water sampled in a LSC vial, which is standardized by TDCR counting, and m is the mass of the water sampled (i.e. poured) in the LSC vial. The relative standard uncertainty of A_m , δ_{A_m} , is given by:

$$\delta_{A_m} = \sqrt{\delta_{A_{TDCR}}^2 + \delta_m^2} \quad (4)$$

where $\delta_{A_{TDCR}}$ and δ_m are the relative standard uncertainties of A_{TDCR} and m , respectively.

It should be noted here that no measurement is shared between the standardization of the volume activity (A_V) and the mass activity (A_m). In this sense it is claimed that A_V and A_m standardizations are completely independent. This allows for a cross-check of the production of a radonated water standard with the new system. The criterion for the cross check is to compare whether A_V and A_m give coherent results taking into account the conditions of the filling the system with water. Quantitatively, a production of a radonated water standard is considered successful when the following equation is satisfied within the estimated uncertainties:

$$A_V = \rho A_m \quad (5)$$

where A_V and A_m are determined according to Equations 1 and 3 ρ is the density and their uncertainties are determined according to Equations 2 and 4, respectively.

2.3 The defined solid angle standard

The radon primary standard was initially developed at LNHB in 1996 [5], recently upgraded [8], and is utilized in numerous international comparisons [9] [10]. This system operates based on the defined solid angle method [11] with a cryogenic radon source. Through a high vacuum and a cold finger maintained at 80 K, ^{222}Rn , produced from a ^{226}Ra source, is frozen in front of a collimated silicon detector. By precisely measuring the collimator size and the source-collimator distance, we can calculate the solid angle and, subsequently, derive the detection efficiency of the system, which is $2.019(6)\cdot 10^{-3}$. This setup allows radon standardization with a typical relative standard uncertainty as low as 0.3 %, subject to the counting statistics during measurement. Once the measurement is completed, the radon standard is transferred using a cryogenic bath into a metal container, such as the one directly connected to the radonated water system (GAZ 11 in Figure 2).

2.4 TDCR and LSC counting methods.

Measurements devices

The Triple to Double Coincidence Ratio (TDCR) method requires the use of a three photomultiplier tubes working in coincidence. The TDCR counters employed in these experiments include the mini-TDCR and micro-TDCR, both developed at LNE-LNHB and validated through multiple comparisons [12].

For the mini-TDCR a custom power supply set to a positive voltage of 900 V, the maximum rated voltage for the photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) was used. The TDCR acquisition is performed with a nanoTDCR module from Yantel[®] [13], which enables simultaneous data acquisition with two different dead times. Consequently, measurements were repeated twice, producing a minimum of four results with dead times of 20 μs , 50 μs , 100 μs , and 150 μs , allowing for the application of the extrapolation method detailed in Section 3.2.

For the micro-TDCR setup, the PMTs were supplied with a positive voltage of 1000 V through a custom high-voltage power supply. Pulses were then amplified using a fast amplifier CAEN N978 and subsequently connected to a CAEN DT5751 digitizer, featuring four channels with $1 \text{ GS}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ sampling rate and 10-bit resolution. This configuration enables list-mode data analysis using Rust software developed in previous studies [14]. The data are analysed with an automatic Python software developed to run the Rust software with a broad range of dead-time analysis variations from $10 \mu\text{s}$ to $500 \mu\text{s}$ (value above $500 \mu\text{s}$ are possible but not relevant in this study); the results are then directly corrected for accidental coincidences [15] and radon half-life decay.

The commercial liquid scintillation counting (LSC) system is the RackBeta 1214 by LKB (manufactured in 1986), operating with coincidence counting using two PMTs. Calibration was performed with liquid scintillation vials containing radon in water, using TDCR measurements from the mini-TDCR. Samples were measured individually to avoid interference from other radonated water vials in the sample changer system of RackBeta. This is essential due to the limited shielding of the LSC counting system, which was originally designed for pure beta emitters.

All liquid scintillation measurements were conducted using 20 mL liquid scintillation vials completely filled with UltimaGold™ AB and the sampled water. The selected vials were made of polyethylene, coated with PTFE, as they demonstrated good stability over time compared to glass vials. The vial caps are lined with aluminium foil, ensuring a secure seal and effectively retaining radon in the cocktail.

Measurements analysis for TDCR without extrapolation

We consider an homogeneous mixture of radonated water with a water-miscible liquid scintillation (LS) cocktail. The measurement of the LS source starts 5 hours after preparation in order to reach secular equilibrium between radon and its short-lived progeny (i.e. not considering ^{210}Po and its daughters). The total activity of the source at secular equilibrium is calculated by:

$$A_{total} = A_{Rn-222} + A_{Po-218} + A_{Pb-214} + A_{Bi-214} + A_{Po-214} \quad (6)$$

Thus, using the data of Table 1, the global counting rate of the source is:

$$N_{total} = A_{Rn-222} (\varepsilon_{Rn-222} + 1.00056 \times \varepsilon_{Po-218} + 1.00547 \times \varepsilon_{Pb-214} + 1.0091 \times \varepsilon_{Bi-214} + 1.0091 \times \varepsilon_{Po-214}) \quad (7)$$

The detection efficiency of ^{222}Rn and ^{218}Po is equal to one, as both nuclides are alpha emitters. The detection efficiency of ^{214}Po is 100% when its decay does not occur during the dead-time of the counter. If ^{214}Bi is detected, the probability of detection of ^{214}Po is $(1 - \exp(-\lambda\tau))$, where λ is the decay constant of ^{214}Po and τ is the dead-time duration. Thus, the detection efficiency of ^{214}Po is:

$$\varepsilon_{Po-214} = 1.0091 \times ((1 - \varepsilon_{Bi-214}^*) + \varepsilon_{Bi-214}^* \times (1 - \exp(-\lambda\tau))) \quad (8)$$

Where ε_{Bi-214}^* is the probability that the decay of ^{214}Bi starts the dead-time of the counter. For the nanoTDCR acquisition system based on the MAC3 logic [13], [16], the dead-time is triggered when the decay is detected in any PMT, i.e. not necessarily in coincidence.

Strictly speaking, the dead-time duration to consider is not the base dead-time duration, but a mean dead-time extended by any pulse occurring during the dead-time. This only concerns the radionuclides of the decay chain of ^{222}Rn uncorrelated with the decay of ^{214}Bi . Thus this contribution, depending of the count rate, is evaluated considering a Poisson distribution of the pulses during the dead-time duration (see below).

The global detection efficiency of the radonated water by the TDCR method is calculated by a locally developed FORTRAN code, Rn222TDCR, using the acquisition data (single, double and triple counting rates), the dead-time base duration and the half-life of ^{214}Po . The detection efficiency of alpha emitters are supposed to be unity and the detection efficiency of the two beta emitters are calculated using the free parameter model in TDCR counting. It is worth noticing that the distribution of the energy deposited in the scintillator is determined by Monte Carlo simulation with the PENELOPE [17] code. This is necessary in this case, as, for such high-energy beta emitters, electrons can escape from the scintillator and do not contribute to the detection efficiency. In the case of ^{214}Bi , Figure 5 shows the significant difference between the theoretical beta spectrum and the deposited energy distribution in the scintillator. The theoretical spectra considered are linear combinations of beta spectra

calculated with the BETASHAPE code [18] after neglecting the beta transitions with probabilities lower than one percent and after normalization of the global beta decay to unity. As the energy of the beta electrons is high, the contribution of gamma-ray absorption to the detection efficiency is neglected. The contribution of Cerenkov emission to the detection efficiency is also neglected, as the PENELOPE model does not include this effect. Therefore, the global detection efficiency calculated is slightly underestimated but this bias is taken into account in the uncertainty evaluation.

This type of TDCR determination of radon activity is termed “Rn-222 code” and has to be distinguished from the determination by extrapolation to zero dead-time, presented later. The main components considered for the relative standard uncertainty evaluation are:

- i. Experimental standard deviation of the double (D) and triple (T) counting rates and standard uncertainty of the TDCR value (depending on the experiment);
- ii. Influence of the kB value in the TDCR model. Even considering a large kB interval from $0.007 \text{ cm}\cdot\text{MeV}^{-1}$ to $0.015 \text{ cm}\cdot\text{MeV}^{-1}$, the influence of this factor is less than 0.001%, due to the high energy of the beta particles depositing energy to the scintillator;
- iii. The influence of the ^{214}Po half-life was evaluated considering the DDEP half-life evaluation of $162.3 (12) \mu\text{s}$. For a dead-time base duration of $50 \mu\text{s}$, the contribution of the ^{214}Po half-life uncertainty to the relative standard uncertainty of the detection efficiency is 0.04%;
- iv. The contribution of the uncertainty of the spectrum calculation is evaluated to 0.6% (taking into account beta shape spectra, gamma absorption, Monte Carlo simulation of the electron energies absorbed by the scintillator, simplification of the decay scheme and no consideration of the Cerenkov effect).

Measurements analysis for TDCR with extrapolation

The extrapolation to zero dead time is performed using data from the CAEN module by varying the dead time value and analysing the corresponding data. A Python-based software tool enables fitting the results using the following function:

$$D(\tau) = a + b * \exp(-\ln(2)/c * \tau) \quad (9)$$

Where τ is the dead-time base duration and a , b and c are fitting parameters. An example for two different samples is presented in Figure 6; the results include the corrections for accidental coincidences, decay during measurements and decay to a reference date. In the case of the nanoTDCR measurements the same extrapolation is used however with only 4 points. The obtained results are then used with the Rn222TDCR code considering zero dead time.

2.5 Gamma-ray spectrometry method

Four high-purity germanium (HPGe) spectrometers were used for the measurement of the radonated water samples. Their main characteristics are summarized in Table 2. The samples activity is measured following the process described below with the corresponding uncertainties calculated according to [19].

Efficiency calibration

The efficiency calibration of the spectrometers is established for different geometrical conditions (point and volume sources) and source-to-detectors distances, as specified in Table 2. Calibration is carried out using standard sources prepared at the LNE-LNHB, from radioactive solutions whose mass activity has been accurately determined by different primary methods.

For each geometrical condition and each energy, E , the full-energy peak (FEP) efficiency, $\varepsilon(E)$, is derived from the peak area (net counting), according to:

$$\varepsilon(E) = \frac{N(E)}{A \cdot I(E) \cdot t} \prod_i C_i \quad (10)$$

where A is the activity of the standard radionuclide (Bq), $I(E)$ is the emission intensity of the line with energy E taken from the DDEP recommended data [6], t is the acquisition duration (live time) (seconds), C_i stands for different correction factors accounting for:

- i. the radioactive decay between the reference time and acquisition start time:

$$C_T = \exp\left(-\ln(2) \cdot \frac{(T_m - T_0)}{T_{1/2}}\right) \quad (11)$$

where T_m is the acquisition start time (when the measurement is carried out), T_0 is the reference time (when the reference activity is known), $T_{1/2}$ is the ^{222}Rn half-life, as measurements are performed once radon and its daughters have reached equilibrium.

ii. the decay during measurement:

$$C_{Dec} = \frac{\ln(2) \cdot \frac{T_r}{T_{1/2}}}{1 - \exp\left(-\ln(2) \cdot \frac{T_r}{T_{1/2}}\right)} \quad (12)$$

where T_r is the real acquisition time (total duration of acquisition),

iii. the true coincidence summing effect:

Contrary to the first two corrective factors, which are the same for a specific standard radionuclide, the coincidence-summing effect is due to the decay scheme of the measured radionuclide and associated corrective factors depends on each energy. Here these are computed using the ETNA software [20, 21].

For practical use, to derive the efficiency for any energy, the set of experimental data (energies and efficiencies) are processed to obtain an efficiency curve as a function of photon energy. ACORES is a software, developed by the LNE-LNHB, used to get the calibration curve as a polynomial function by applying the chi-2 minimisation method [22]. A key feature is the ability to take into account correlations between input data through a covariance matrix. Here, for each radionuclide, the correlation factor corresponds to the source activity uncertainty, which is a common uncertainty parameter.

An example of the experimental data and the resulting calibration curve in the range from 100 keV to 2 000 keV for detector G8 is plotted in Figure 7. It was obtained using seventeen standard radionuclides and the resulting relative uncertainty on the fitted values is about 0.5 %.

The fitted calibration curves versus the energy for several geometrical conditions for detector GEHPIC are compared in Figure 8.

Activity measurement

Once the calibration curve is available, one can derive the activity of a sample as:

$$A = \frac{N(E)}{\varepsilon(E) \cdot I(E) \cdot t \prod_j C_j} \quad (13)$$

Only selected source-detector geometries have been used for the efficiency calibration of spectrometers (Table 2). If one wishes to measure samples with a different shape or position, it is necessary to calculate a corrective factor to account for the geometry change. This is computed using the software ETNA [21]. The calculation is based on the assumption that the detector efficiency is a combination of the intrinsic efficiency of the detector, which depends only on the energy, and of geometric factors depending on both the photon energy and the measurement geometry. This geometric factor is calculated by including the solid angle of detection and any attenuation effects in the source and container material.

As presented in section 2.2, the samples are conditioned either in a 50 cm³ or 100 cm³ volume. To ensure that the geometry correction factor between calibration and measurement is as close as possible to 1, the 50 cm³ gas container has been designed with the same dimensions as the so-called ‘‘SG50’’ calibration volume, with the exception of the container walls which are made of 0.5 mm stainless steel instead of 1.2 mm polyethylene. For example, at 10 cm from the detector window, the geometry correction factors are 1.02 and 1.03 for 352 keV and 609 keV, respectively. For each detector, the measurement sequence includes recording a background spectrum (240 000 s) without any containers, before measuring the samples. It is subtracted from the counting spectrum (proportionally to the counting live time) before determining the net peak areas, with the dedicated deconvolution software COLEGRAM [23] being used for overlapping peaks. The correction factors, efficiency transfer from

calibration geometry (SG50 10 cm) to measurement geometry and coincidence summing in the measurement conditions, are calculated using ETNA.

The activity of ^{222}Rn cannot be directly measured through its gamma-ray emission ($E = 510$ (2) keV), whose emission is questionable. However, it can be derived via the activity of its two progenies, ^{214}Pb and ^{214}Bi , which are quickly in equilibrium with the parent nuclide. Both are multi-gamma emitters and they can easily be quantified using their most intense peak, respectively 351.932 (2) keV (intensity: 35.60 (7) %) and 609.312 (7) keV (intensity: 45.49 (19) %) for ^{214}Pb and ^{214}Bi . To derive the activity of ^{222}Rn , the resulting activity of each daughter must be multiplied by an additional corrective factor to account for the activity ratio between ^{222}Rn and its progenies when the radioactive equilibrium is reached (see Table 1)

The GS measurements were conducted with several objectives:

- i. Checking the homogeneity of sampling by measuring several containers at the same sample-to detector distance,
- ii. Measuring the activity of individual containers at different source-to detector distances, to define the most suitable measurement conditions,
- iii. Measuring any residual activity when the container is emptied;
- iv. Demonstrating the deposition of solid daughters on the container's walls.

3. Results

3.1 Production of radon in water standard with the new system

Production of radonated water

Producing radonated water is particularly challenging due to the necessity of avoiding any gas phase in the circuit, as this could lead to radon desorption from the water into air gaps. The following preparatory steps are therefore essential and must be completed before the preparation of radonated water. Strict adherence to this protocol is required:

- i. The radon standard, produced under vacuum in volume GAZ11, is connected to the system. All valves on the standard and in the circuit are initially closed.
- ii. The entire system is evacuated to a vacuum of 10^{-6} hPa.
- iii. The degassed water tank is filled with enough water to supply V_{21} , and the water is degassed by pumping.
- ii. Once degassed, V_{21} is isolated, and B_{30} is opened, allowing degassed water to fill V_{21} . Clean water is then dispensed through the tubing by opening either B_{31} and B_{24} or B_{30} , ensuring all required tubing, including the Dispensette[®], is entirely filled with water.
- iii. B_{21} and B_{24} are then closed while B_{30} remains open to enable further degassing of the water tank, ensuring that no gas remains in the small tubing within V_{21} .
- iv. After this, the tank is filled fully with water, and degassing is completed by pumping.

After these steps, the remaining system, held under vacuum at 10^{-6} hPa, is ready for water injection. Trials have shown that omitting any of these steps jeopardizes the preparation of radon in water samples.

To transfer radon into water, the gaseous radon standard must first be frozen in the gas volume, using a liquid nitrogen bath. The partial pressure of radon at the temperature of liquid nitrogen is negligible, i.e. at this temperature radon is 100% frozen on the walls in contact with the bath. Once frozen, and after ensuring the system maintains an optimal vacuum, all valves are closed except B_{30} . Sequentially, each B valve is then opened from the top of the system down to B_{11} and B_{10} , the valves on the frozen standard. It is essential to wait until each opened volume is filled with water before proceeding to the next valve, allowing water to gradually fill each section.

When the water reaches the radon standard valves (i.e. GAZ11 valves), these are opened one by one. The water fills the vial, immediately freezing, after which the nitrogen bath is removed. The frozen water is then allowed to thaw back into liquid form, with B_{30} open to maintain pressure equilibrium in the circuit. Under these conditions, radon fully dissolves into the water in GAZ11. To isolate the water supply volume, B_{24} is then closed, and the water is circulated with the entire system with the pump in both directions for at least 30 minutes to ensure thorough mixing. The pump flow rate is set to $1 \text{ L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, while the total volume is less than 1 L.

Once all experimental processes are completed, all water is removed from the circuit by opening all valves once each container is returned to its original position. Very dry air is then circulated through the system to remove any residual water, a process lasting several hours. Afterward, the vacuum pump operates for 24 hours to remove any remaining water traces, ensuring the circuit is ready for the next experiment.

Volume measurement

To determine the volume activity of radonated water, a precise measurement of the system's total volume is required. As illustrated in Figure 2, a reference volume, V_{ref} , is connected to the circuit. This stainless-steel volume, certified by the LNE, is $V_{ref} = 2\,223.6\ (1)\ \text{cm}^3$ and is used to measure the entire circuit volume using the ideal gas law. In brief, the reference container is pressurized with gas to a known pressure, P_{ref} , and temperature, T_{ref} , while the rest of the circuit remains under vacuum. Subsequently, the valve on V_{ref} is opened, allowing the gas to expand into the pipe volume, and P_{tube} and T_{tube} are measured to calculate V_{tube} . While V_{tube} , calculated by Equation 14, is not directly used for radonated water production, it represents the combined volume of V_1 and V_2 in Figure 2.

$$\frac{P_{ref} V_{ref}}{T_{ref}} = \frac{P_{tube} V_{tube}}{T_{tube}} \quad (14)$$

This procedure is repeated to measure $V_y = V_{tube} + V_x$ by recording T_y and P_y where V_x represents the volume of a specified section or the entirety of the functional circuit in the system. The volume of interest is then calculated using the same equation as before, namely:

$$V_x = \left(\frac{T_y}{P_y} - \frac{T_{tube}}{P_{tube}} \right) \frac{P_{ref} V_{ref}}{T_{ref}} \quad (15)$$

This process and calculation were used to measure each volume within the circuit as well as the total useful volume of the new system. The results are summarised in Table 3. It is important to emphasise that disconnecting and reconnecting the sample for GS does not affect the volume measurement. The uncertainties in Table 3 reflect the combination of measurement uncertainties and the relative standard deviation of results from repeated measurements. All measurements were performed within a temperature range of 20°C to 31°C, measured in the circuit. Therefore, the standard deviation also accounts for any potential thermal expansion of the entire system, although this effect is likely negligible within this operational range.

As the volume of the system V_{sys} is determined with high precision, further attention is paid to study and verify that V_{sys} is entirely filled with water. This is done by visual inspection for bubbles during the water cycling phase in the preparation of the radonated water. The glass parts in volumes V_{16} and V_{18} are monitored continuously during the water cycling phase for air bubbles. Typically, no air bubbles are observed in the circulating water with only millimeter sized bubbles occurring rarely. This monitoring is twofold: to avoid rough errors (i.e. large air bubbles existing in the system) and to estimate the maximum amount of air bubbles that can be available in the system. A correction factor k_V is introduced in Eq. 1, to account for the filling of V_{sys} with water. Typically no bubbles are found in the system and the value of the factor is equal to 1, but its uncertainty accounts for the estimates of the maximal volume of the air bubbles that can be hidden in the system. The uncertainty of k_V accounts also for the gradient of the water filling the system and for the estimated density of the water in the gaz volumes (see below).

Sampling Testing

An additional challenge in developing this system was the integration of a water sampling mechanism. The aim was to accurately sample a specific volume of radonated water directly into liquid scintillator within scintillation vials for the calibration of liquid scintillation counters. By design sampling of water by pulling with a syringe is strictly avoided, as this typically creates underpressure during the pulling process and thus cannot guarantee 100% radon-loss-free sampling. To overcome this difficulty, we designed a pushing sampling mechanism, which relies on pushing the water through the LSC part of the system with radon free water. The pushing device is a Dispensette® (shown in the bottom left of Figure 3) which can push distilled water through the system. It allows volume selection from 1 mL to 10 mL with a manufacturer-certified uncertainty of 0.1%.

The LSC sampling is carried out by inserting a needle into a liquid scintillation vial containing 10 mL of Ultima Gold AB (UG-AB) liquid scintillator. The needle is located on a convenience place at the lower end of the LSC part of the system (see Fig. 2). Water is dispensed slowly in the scintillator to prevent air contact with the radonated water, with the scintillator preventing radon escape. After dispensing, the needle is carefully withdrawn, and additional liquid scintillator is added to top

off the vial. This process is illustrated in [7]. The procedure ensures that the vial is sealed without air bubbles and shaken to achieve complete mixing. The mass of injected water is determined by weighing the vial with only the scintillator and then with both scintillator and radonated water. In over 35 samples of 5 mL prepared directly in scintillation vials, the average water mass was measured as 5.014 g, with a relative standard deviation of 0.4%. The relative standard uncertainty of the mass measurement was 0.1%, indicating minimal deviation in the sampling system, likely due to a small amount of liquid scintillator clinging to the needle.

Measurement of the amount of the water in the GS volumes

The amount of water contained in the GS volumes is measured after the GS measurement using the following procedure:

- i. For the GS measurement the GS volumes (GAZ1, GAZ5, GAZ7, GAZ9, and GAZ11) are disconnected from the system and are kept closed. The inlet and outlet of each (Figure 3) are carefully flushed with dry air. After flushing, the inlet and outlet are connected to the vacuum system and evacuated to a vacuum level of approximately 10^{-5} hPa. Achieving this vacuum ensures no residual water remains in the outside parts of the valves of the GAZ volumes.
- ii. The GS measurement is then performed.
- iii. After the GS measurement, the mass of each full volume is measured using a balance (Mettler PM4800, resolution 0.01 g, standard uncertainty of 0.1 g).
- iv. The water is then evacuated from the volume, which is flushed with clean, dry air. The volume is connected to the vacuum system again and evacuated to approximately 10^{-5} hPa to ensure no residual water remains inside. The valves are then closed.
- v. The mass of the empty GAZ volume (under vacuum) is measured using the same balance.
- vi. The mass of the water in the GAZ volume is calculated as the difference between the masses obtained in steps 3 and 5.

This procedure is repeated across several experiments, with results shown in Table 4. The results indicate that the relative standard deviation of the water mass in the GAZ volumes is higher than the standard deviation of the mass measurements (which is around 0.1%). This increased variance may be due to variations in the density of the water at the time of filling. Analysing the results from various experiments does not reveal a systematic correlation between the estimated water density in the GAZ volumes and the temperature during volume or system closure. The dependence of the water density on the temperature is taken from [24]. Consequently, this variability is accounted for by adding an uncertainty component to the uncertainty of k_V , accounting for the water amount in each experiment, attributed to the water density in the system.

Notably, this measurement is sensitive enough to detect even the mass of air contained in the GAZ volumes. For example, in one experiment, the mass of volume GAZ1 at step 5 (i.e., under vacuum) was 524.503 (58) g, with the value in parentheses indicating the standard deviation of 5 balance readings. After opening the volume and filling it with room air, its mass increased to 524.623 (57) g. The estimated air mass in the volume was thus 0.12 g, corresponding to an air density of $1.1 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, consistent with the expected room air density ($1.15 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$). Similar results were obtained for the other volumes (not shown).

As the system is used over time, additional knowledge about the water content in the GAZ volumes and the water density in each experiment will accumulate. This information is crucial because, in our experience, the water mass in the GAZ volumes is a strong indicator for identifying systematic errors during radonated water preparation with this system.

3.2 LSC measurements of the radon concentrations

RackBeta Results

The calibration of the RackBeta 1214 counter was conducted prior these experiments with liquid scintillation vials containing radonated water, using TDCR measurements from the mini-TDCR. The estimated efficiency of the RackBeta 1214 for ^{222}Rn in equilibrium with its short-lived progeny in a fully filled LSC vial containing 18 g of UG-AB cocktail and 5 g of radonated water was found to be 4.950 (75) g. The fact that the RackBeta 1214 counter has only lead shielding and lacks active shielding is advantageous for ^{222}Rn measurements, as active shielding, if present, could be triggered by gamma rays emitted during the decays of ^{214}Po and ^{214}Bi , leading to the loss of true events and decreased efficiency. However, a disadvantage of the counter is that if there is a sample in the sample holder while another sample is being measured, the former may contribute to the counting rate of the sample being measured due to interactions of ^{214}Po and ^{214}Bi gamma-rays with the LSC cocktail. For this reason, the samples were measured one by one. The typical uncertainty budget for the RackBeta measurements is given in Table 5.

TDCR measurements

TDCR measurements were performed with two devices using two different calculation approaches for each device. The miniTDCR values were obtained either by extrapolation of the four values corresponding to four different dead times, or by using a single result (at $DT = 50 \mu s$) processed with the Rn222TDCR calculation code. For microTDCR, these measurements were carried out using the CAEN module and analysed with the Python code mentioned in Section 2.4 for extrapolation, as well as with the Rn-222TDCR code.

The Python software allows processing CAEN list-mode data with various dead times for extrapolation. We leveraged this capability to test the Rn-222TDCR code and perform calculations with multiple dead times for the same sample. The results of each calculation are presented in Figure 9. While the figure shows a slight variation at higher dead times, the overall relative standard deviation is 0.06%, demonstrating that the correction applied by the TDCR code performs very well.

As presented in Figure 10, some of the monitored samples showed a small variation in the T/D ratio over time. The most significant change is illustrated in this figure, with a T/D variation of 0.18% observed more than two days after sample preparation. This change is greater than expected from the growth of ^{210}Pb , which accounts for only 0.01% of the ^{222}Rn activity and is therefore negligible compared to this observation. It is also noteworthy that a similar variation is observed in the D counting rate, with a change of 0.22% after more than two days.

We suspect that this phenomenon may be related either to the deposition of solid daughter of ^{222}Rn or to the presence of a small air bubble in the vial. However, the second hypothesis could not be confirmed, as this sample showed the greatest variation but not the largest air bubble. These observations led us to decide to perform TDCR measurements shortly after sample preparation, in order to minimize fluctuations that are negligible within a single day of experimentation.

3.3 Gamma-spectrometry measurements of the radon concentrations

As mentioned earlier, GS was used for different purposes. Here are the main results:

Homogeneity between containers

Four containers prepared in the same set (GAZ1, GAZ5, GAZ 7 and GAZ9) were measured in the same experimental conditions, the homogeneity results show a standard deviation of 1% when samples are measured at 10 cm. This value is included in the activity uncertainty budget.

Measurements at different distances

The same container was measured at three distances from the detector window. It was stated that the activity measured close “at contact” is significantly lower than the one measured at 10 cm and 20 cm, and lower than the reference value, as shown in Figures 11 and 12 for the two series of experiments. This can be explained by an inhomogeneity in the radionuclides repartition, mainly due to the solid daughters of ^{222}Rn that can migrate towards the container walls, what is discussed in the following sections.

Measurement of residual activity

After the measurement of the container, it was carefully emptied and dried to remove the radonated water. The empty container was measured again and revealed a residual apparent activity (representing about 25% of the initial counting rate), thus demonstrating that part of the solid progenies are fixed on the container walls.

Confirmation by convection experiment

Another specific experiment was carried out to demonstrate our hypothesis of the fixation of solid progenies on the walls: the container was first measured for 10 000 s then frozen to force convection. A new measurement resulted in a counting rate increase of about 12% for both ^{214}Pb and ^{214}Bi , what could be due to resuspension of solid progenies.

Monte Carlo simulations

Additional calculations using Monte Carlo simulation were performed using the PENELOPE code [17]. The geometry model includes the “GeHP1C” detector with the GAZ11 container (50 cm^3) filled of water placed at 4.5 mm, 100 mm and 200 mm

from the detector window, corresponding to experimental results presented in Table 8. The simulations were run for the energies of the main gamma-rays ^{214}Pb or ^{214}Bi , considering two cases: homogeneous or surface repartition. In the first case, the radionuclide is homogeneously distributed within the water volume, and in the second case, it is concentrated on a thin layer (1 mm) on the container walls. The simulation demonstrates that, at a short distance between the source and the detector, the impact on the detection efficiency for deposited progeny in relation to the homogeneous volume is close to 8% and, as expected, becomes negligible at a distance of more than 10 cm.

However, the effect of the radionuclides repartition in the container is not easy to determine. For example, if the deposition occurs entirely at the bottom of the vial, it can lead to almost a factor of 2 in terms of detection efficiency.

Assuming that there is a 1-mm thick deposit of 10% of the activity directly at the bottom of the container, and 90% homogeneous distribution in the rest of the volume, the MC simulation gives efficiency ratios (relative to a completely homogeneous distribution) of 1.14, 1.07 and 1.01 for the 4.5 mm, 100 mm and 200 mm respectively. These findings correspond well to the trend that was observed experimentally.

Mass activity measurement

Based on the analyses conducted, the most suitable geometry for GS measurements appears to be the furthest measurement with the smallest volume. A summary of these results is presented in Figures 11 and 12. The typical uncertainty budget for a distance of 20 cm is provided in Table 7.

3.4 Comparison between the results of the different methods.

Several experiments were conducted with the new system to test its capabilities and compare different methods for measuring ^{222}Rn in water. The results of the first experiment are summarized in Table 8 and Figure 11. In this experiment, six LSC and three GS samples were prepared from the system's water. The relative uncertainty of the values reported by the LSC methods (including TDCR) is calculated as the square root of the sum of the squares of the relative uncertainty of the individual measurement and the relative uncertainty due to variability between the samples. The latter is estimated from the standard deviation of the measured activities across the samples. The GS samples were measured using three different geometries: at 20 cm, 10 cm, and directly on top of the HPGe detector (at contact).

Overall, the results from the first experiment show strong consistency between the different techniques, within the estimated uncertainties. The only exception are the GS measurements at close geometries (10 cm and at contact), where the results are biased compared to the others. This bias is likely due to the deposition of some of the of radon progeny on the walls of the container, as discussed in Section 3.3. Given the coherence between the solid angle and TDCR measurement results, the radonated water mass activity can be standardized using both methods.

We opted to standardize based on the results from the defined solid angle measurements, as this method is the primary standard used for radon-in-air standardizations and serves as the foundation of the radon-in-air traceability chain. Table 9 shows the uncertainty budget for this experiment, indicating that the primary contributor to the overall uncertainty is the corrective factor k_V that accounts for the condition of the water during the filling of the system and the transfer of radon into water (see Section 3.1 for details). Nevertheless, it appears that the mass activity of the water in this experiment can be standardized with a relative uncertainty of approximately 0.6%. While the volume activity relative standard uncertainty can go down to 0.40% if the condition of experiments, especially temperatures, are well controlled.

Similar results were obtained in the second experiment, as shown in Table 10 and Figure 12. Again, there is excellent agreement between the methods, except for the GS measurement at contact, which again shows a systematic bias. The uncertainty budget (Table 11) reveals that the main source of uncertainty is the determination of the water density after sealing the system. The analysis shows that the specific activity of water can be standardized with a relative standard uncertainty of 0.8%. Similar results and agreement between the methods were also observed in pilot experiments conducted with the pilot version of the system [7].

Finally, we conducted these experiments under the worst-case temperature scenario, i.e., with significant temperature variations due to a faulty air conditioning system at the time of measurements. It is important to note that our conservative approach to estimating uncertainty takes this into account. Therefore, significantly better uncertainty could be achieved with a stable temperature throughout the experiment, allowing for a more precise determination of water density during the measurements.

4. Conclusions

The new radonated water system developed in this study allows for the completely independent standardization of the radonated water specific activity by two primary methods. By "completely independent," it is meant that no measurement is shared between the two standardization methods.

In the TDCR method, standardization in terms of mass activity is achieved by the TDCR measurement and measurement of the mass of the water sample.

In the defined solid angle method, standardization is based on the DSA measurement, along with the measurement of the system's volume for volume activity determination. The latter is performed retrospectively through mass and volume measurements (see Section 3.1), the mass measurements being carried out using a different balance, ensuring complete independence from the mass measurements used for the TDCR method.

As a result, the DSA and TDCR standardizations are considered to be fully independent. The agreement between these two methods in the preparation of a standardized radon-in-water source is regarded as a strong criterion for the quality of the prepared source. The results of this study indicate that the mass-specific activity of the radon-in-water sources can be standardized with a relative standard uncertainty of less than 1%.

The design of the system allows various cross-checks during the preparation of the radonated water, for instance: optical inspection of the water circulation, sensitive tests about the amount of the water in the gas systems, comparison of two primary standards. Together, all these measurements ensure that the preparation of traceable radonated water, which is by no means a difficult and cumbersome task, has gone smoothly and without systematic errors. On top of that we propose a new standard for radon with a solution for two measurands, $\text{Bq}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ for the radonated water standard which corresponds to the need of Euratom directive [1] and $\text{Bq}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ for TDCR measurement and comparisons.

Furthermore, this study highlights the limitations of gamma spectrometry for measuring radon-in-water. The phenomenon of progeny deposition on the walls of the GS containers introduces differences between the calibration and measurement geometries. The effect of these differences is difficult to be quantified but can cause significant bias in the measurement results, especially under experimental conditions optimized for low-activity detection (i.e. close measurement geometries). Variations exceeding 10% can be expected, making it essential to take precautions when using GS. This also calls for a revision of the measurement standards established for gamma-ray spectrometry determination of radon in drinking water.

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FIGURES

Figure 1. Complete decay scheme of ^{222}Rn , the light colored isotopes are negligible due to their very low branch ratio or to their long half-life. Decay scheme extracted from Laraweb based on DDEP data [5].

Figure 2. Diagram of the radon-in-water setup with all components. "B" refers to the valve numbers and "V" to the volumes between the valves. Two lines are visually identified: one corresponds to the sampling for GS (in yellow), and the other for LSC sampling (in grey).

Figure 3. A photograph of the radon-in-water standard production system at LNE-LNHB. The GS sampling part is on the left side and the LSC sampling part is on the right side (see also Fig. 2)

Figure 4. The GS volumes with the VCR® connectors.

Figure 5. Difference between BetaShape spectra emitted and the absorbed spectra in the liquid scintillator simulated with PENELOPE in plastic liquid scintillation vial filled with Ultima Gold™ AB with 5 mL of water.

Figure 6. Example of D counting rate as a function of dead time from 10 μs to 500 μs used for the analysis of the data from the digitizer.

Figure 7. Experimental efficiency calibration of detector G8 for point sources at 10 cm. The lower panel displays the relative residuals between the fitted values and the experimental ones.

Figure 8. Experimental efficiency calibration of detector GeHP1C for the three different experimental conditions using the same standard SG50 (liquid solution with 50 mL volume in plastic container). Typical relative standard uncertainties are about 1.5%, 1.2% and 0.8% for the measurement distances: contact, 10 cm and 20 cm, respectively.

Figure 9. Calculated mass activity of sample 5 from experiment #2 as a function of dead time with Rn-222 code, validation.

Figure 10. Evolution of D (upper panel) and T/D (lower panel) counting rates corrected for radon decay and T/D over time.

Figure 11. Comparisons between the results of the different methods obtained in the first experiment. The error bars indicate the overall estimated standard uncertainties.

Figure 12. Comparisons between the results of the different methods obtained in the second experiment. The error bars indicate the overall estimated standard uncertainties.

TABLESTable 1. Relative activities of radon daughters vs. ^{222}Rn activity at equilibrium.

<i>Radionuclide</i>	<i>Relative activity vs. ^{222}Rn</i>
^{222}Rn	1.0
^{218}Po	1.00056 (30)
^{214}Pb	1.00547 (37)
^{214}Bi	1.00910 (43)
^{214}Po	1.00910 (48)

Table 2. Main characteristics of the gamma-ray spectrometers.

<i>Detector identification</i>	<i>G8</i>	<i>G9</i>	<i>GeHP1C</i>	<i>GeHP2b</i>
<i>Type</i>	Coaxial N	Coaxial N	Coaxial N	Coaxial N
<i>Crystal diameter</i>	49.5 mm	48.7 mm	84.8 mm	68.5 mm
<i>Crystal thickness</i>	47.8 mm	55.4 mm	31.9 mm	71.2 mm
<i>Ge dead layer thickness</i>	300 μm	300 μm	200 μm	300 μm
<i>Window material</i>	Be	Be	Carbon-epoxy	Al
<i>Window thickness</i>	500 μm	500 μm	1 mm	2 mm
<i>External shielding</i>	Passive: 5 cm of lead – 2 mm of cadmium - 2 mm of copper	Passive: 5 cm of lead – 2 mm of copper	Passive: 10 cm of lead - 3 mm Stainless steel Active: Anti-cosmic	Passive: 10 cm of lead and 5 mm of copper
<i>Energy resolution (Full Width at Half Maximum at 122 keV)</i>	0.82 keV	0.92 keV	0.70 keV	1.20 keV
<i>Energy resolution (Full Width at Half Maximum at 1 332 keV)</i>	1.82 keV	1.92 keV	1.86 keV	1.90 keV
<i>Point source calibration distance(s)</i>	10 cm and 19 cm	10 cm	10 cm	10 cm
<i>Liquid source (50 cm³) calibration distance(s)</i>	10 cm and 18 cm	8 cm	Contact and 10 cm and 20 cm	Contact and 10 cm
<i>Software</i>	Maestro	Maestro	Interwinner	Interwinner
<i>Acquisition</i>	Ortec 926	Ortec 926	Itech QuadADC	Itech QuadADC

Table 3. Results of measured volumes of the circuit with associated standard uncertainties.

<i>Name of the sample</i>	<i>Volume (cm³)</i>
<i>V_{Total}</i>	672.7 (7)
<i>V_{Gaz11}</i>	49.32 (14)
<i>V_{Gaz9}</i>	105.45 (20)
<i>V_{Gaz7}</i>	105.08 (27)
<i>V_{Gaz5}</i>	104.28 (25)
<i>V_{Gaz1}</i>	106.06 (15)
<i>V₁ + V₂</i>	29.30 (17)
<i>V₃</i>	4.17 (7)
<i>V₄</i>	3.01 (30)
<i>V₆</i>	5.72 (8)
<i>V₈</i>	4.39 (15)
<i>V₉</i>	9.90 (14)
<i>V₁₀</i>	13.55 (9)
<i>V₁₂</i>	5.41 (8)
<i>V₁₄</i>	4.94 (18)
<i>V₁₆</i>	13.25 (15)
<i>V₁₇</i>	5.53 (19)
<i>V₁₈</i>	12.44 (16)
<i>V₁₉</i>	120.55 (6)
<i>V₂₀</i>	5.03 (27)

Table 4. Average masses of the water in the gas volumes estimated on the basis of different experiments.

<i>Volume</i>	<i>No of experiments</i>	<i>Average mass of the water in the GAZ volumes</i>		<i>Estimated average density of the water in the GAZ volumes</i>	
		<i>Mass and standard uncertainty, g</i>	<i>Relative standard uncertainty, %</i>	<i>Density and standard uncertainty, g/cm³</i>	<i>Relative standard uncertainty, %</i>
<i>GAZ1</i>	4	105.28(18)	0.17	0.9927(16)	0.17
<i>GAZ5</i>	4	103.72(26)	0.25	0.9947(25)	0.25
<i>GAZ7</i>	2	104.48(40)	0.38	0.9953(38)	0.38
<i>GAZ9</i>	3	104.60(10)	0.10	0.9920(87)	0.09
<i>GAZ11</i>	4	48.999(69)	0.14	0.99422(67)	0.07

Table 5. Uncertainty budget for measurements with RackBeta LS counter.

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Typical relative standard uncertainty, %</i>
<i>Efficiency</i>	1.5%
<i>Mass, taking into account drop on the sampling needle</i>	0.4%
<i>Variability across samples</i>	0.5%
<i>Counting statistics and background correction</i>	0.4%
<i>Decay correction with half-life of ²²²Rn</i>	0.003%
<i>Decay correction during measurement</i>	0.04%
<i>Combined relative standard uncertainty</i>	1.7%

Table 6. Typical uncertainty budget for TDCR measurements.

Variable	Typical relative standard uncertainty, %
<i>kB variation from 0.007 to 0.015 cm·MeV⁻¹</i>	< 0.001%
<i>²¹⁴Po half-life or extrapolation to zero dead time</i>	< 0.1%
<i>Beta spectra, gamma interaction, Cherenkov</i>	0.6%
<i>Alpha detection efficiency</i>	< 0.1%
<i>D Counting rate</i>	0.1%
<i>T/D</i>	0.01%
<i>Decay correction with half-life of ²²²Rn</i>	0.003%
<i>Decay correction during measurement</i>	0.04%
<i>Mass, taking into account drop on the sampling needle</i>	0.4%
Combined relative standard uncertainty	0.75%

Table 7. Uncertainty budget for GS with HPGe detector with GAZ 11 at 20 cm from the detector window.

Variable	Typical relative standard uncertainty	
	352 keV	609 keV
<i>Reproducibility of sampling</i>	1.00%	1.00%
<i>Peak area</i>	0.90%	0.90%
<i>Photon emission intensity</i>	0.20%	0.42%
<i>Reference efficiency calibration</i>	0.94%	0.93%
<i>Coincidence summing correction</i>	0.02%	0.02%
<i>Efficiency transfer</i>	0.01%	0.07%
<i>Decay from reference time correction</i>	0.004%	0.004%
<i>Decay during measurement correction</i>	0.002%	0.002%
Combined relative standard uncertainty	1.65%	1.69%

Table 8. Results of the experiment #1.

Radonated water specific activity by different methods*, Bq/g								
Defined solid angle	TDCR and LSC analysis						GS	
	Sample	MiniTDCR Rn-222 code DT = 50 μs	MiniTDCR extrapolation	microTDCR CAEN Rn-222 code DT = 50 μs	microTDCR CAEN extrapolation	LSC – RackBeta 1214	GAZ 11 on GeHP1C	Results
61.79 (39) (0.63%)	SL1_1 *	61.08 (46)	60.90 (46)	61.38 (47)	61.34 (46)	60.34 (91)	at 10 cm	59.2 (13)
	SL1_2 *	61.20 (48)	60.92 (45)	61.36 (47)	61.45 (45)	61.27 (93)		
	SL1_3 *	60.86 (46)	60.81 (46)	61.00 (49)	61.31 (46)	60.94 (92)	at 20 cm	61.5 (12)
	SL1_4 *	60.79 (47)	61.07 (46)	61.22 (47)	61.66 (46)	61.05 (93)		
	SL1_5 *	60.87 (49)	60.83 (46)	61.1 (5)	61.13 (46)	60.98 (92)	at	53.2 (13)
	SL1_6 *	61.38 (48)	61.49 (46)	61.53 (47)	61.56 (46)	61.59 (93)	contact	
	Mean & stdev**	61.03 (23)	61.00 (25)	61.27 (20)	61.41 (19)	61.04 (90)		
Final result ***	61.0 (5)	61.0 (5)	61.26 (53)	61.41 (49)	61.0 (10)			

* The values in the brackets on these lines indicate the estimated standard uncertainty of the measure value.
** The values in the brackets on this line indicate the standard deviation of the results across different samples
*** The values in the brackets on this line indicate the overall estimated standard uncertainty

Table 9. Final values and uncertainty budget for the results of experiment #1.

Variables	Value	Standard uncertainty	Relative standard uncertainty, %
Activity as determined by the defined solid angle method (kBq)	41.38	0.16	0.38%
System volume, experimental (cm ³)	672.73	0.70	0.10%
Water density at closing, experimental (g·cm ⁻³)	0.9956	0.0026	0.26%
Correction factor k_V	1.0000	0.0042	0.42%
Radon-in-water mass specific activity, A_m, (Bq·g⁻¹)	61.79	0.39	0.63%

Table 10. Results of the experiment #2.

Radonated water specific activity by different methods*, Bq/g								
Defined solid angle	TDCR and LSC analysis						GS	Results
	Sample	MiniTDCR Rn-222 code DT = 50 μ s	MiniTDCR extrapolation	microTDCR CAEN Rn-222 code DT = 50 μ s	microTDCR CAEN extrapolation	LSC – RackBeta 1214	Detector and geometry	
48.24 (40) (0.80%)	SL3_1 *	48.06 (36)	48.15 (36)	-	-	-	Gaz 1 on G9 HPGE at contact	46.6 (25)
	SL3_2 *	48.10 (36)	47.75 (36)	48.88 (36)	48.82 (36)	48.48 (76)		
	SL3_3 *	48.42 (35)	47.87 (35)	48.43 (36)	48.41 (36)	48.37 (75)		
	SL3_4 *	48.27 (36)	48.26 (36)	48.55 (36)	48.54 (36)	48.43 (76)	Gaz 11 on G8 HPGe at 10 cm	47.6 (8)
	SL3_5 *	47.75 (36)	48.26 (36)	48.61 (36)	48.63 (36)	48.65 (75)		
	SL3_6 *	48.72 (36)	48.07 (36)	48.77 (36)	48.76 (36)	48.74 (82)		
	Mean & stdev**	48.22 (33)	48.06 (21)	48.65 (18)	48.63 (16)	48.53 (78)		
Final result ***	48.2 (7)	48.1 (6)	48.6 (6)	48.6 (6)	48.53 (82)			

* The values in the brackets on these lines indicate the estimated standard uncertainty of the measure value.

** The values in the brackets on this line indicate the standard deviation of the results across different samples

*** The values in the brackets on this line indicate the overall estimated standard uncertainty

Table 11. Final values and uncertainty budget for the results of experiment #2.

Variables	Value	Standard uncertainty	Relative standard uncertainty, %
Activity as determined by the defined solid angle method (kBq)	32.32	0.13	0.39%
System volume, experimental (cm ³)	671.97	0.70	0.33%
Water density at closing, experimental (g·cm ⁻³)	0.9970	0.0064	0.49%
Correction factor k_V	1.0000	0.0042	0.42%
Radon-in-water mass specific activity, A_m, (Bq·g⁻¹)	48.24	0.40	0.82%